

Physics

Lancaster
University

Status of the Short-Baseline Near Detector at Fermilab

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Overview

- The SBN Program and SBND
- Physics Goals
- Detector Overview
- Detector Performance & Calibration
- Towards First Results!

The Short-Baseline Neutrino Program

- The SBN program is comprised of multiple Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers (LArTPCs) situated along the Booster Neutrino Beam (BNB) at Fermilab
- Purpose is to conclusively understand the anomalous Low Energy Excess observed by MiniBooNE
- SBND has a rich single-detector physics program, focusing on neutrino-argon interactions and searching for beyond standard model physics

ICARUS

- Baseline: 600 m
- LAr: 476 ton
- Taking data: 2021 - present

MicroBooNE

- Baseline: 470 m
- LAr: 89 ton
- Taking data: 2015 - 2021

SBND

This talk!

- Baseline: 110 m
- LAr: 112 ton
- Taking data: 2024 - present

SBN Physics - Oscillation

Dedicated talk on short-baseline neutrino anomalies by Mark Ross-Lonergan yesterday at 11:30am

- As the near detector, SBND will tightly constrain systematic uncertainties associated with the beam flux and ν -Ar cross-sections
- Analysis of ν_e appearance and ν_μ disappearance will be used to conclusively address the sterile neutrino hypothesis as an explanation for the short-baseline anomaly

SBND Physics – Neutrino Interactions

- Per beam-year, it is predicted that SBND will record ~ 2 million ν_μ CC and ~ 15 thousand ν_e CC interactions. This is around 7,000 neutrino interactions per day!
- Unprecedented statistics in SBND allow for precise multidimensional differential measurements for common channels, as well as measuring rare channels
- There is significant overlap with DUNE's kinematic phase space

Dedicated talk on SBND cross-section measurements by Rachel Coackley earlier today (9:30 am)

SBND Physics – Beyond Standard Model

- High statistics and proximity to the beam allows SBND to search for low-mass, low-coupling BSM particles
- Probe alternative BSM explanations of the MiniBooNE anomaly
- Competitive sensitivities to many dark-sector particles
- New sensitivities available in an upcoming paper

Light Dark Matter

Romeri Kelley Machado PRD 2019

Dark Neutrinos

Bertuzzo Jana Machado Zukanovich PRL 2018, PLB 2019
Arguelles Hostert Tsai PRL 2019
Ballett Pascoli Ross-Lonergan PRD 2019
Ballett Hostert Pascoli PRD 2020

Millicharged Particles

Magill, Plestid, Pospelov, Tsai, PRL 2019
Hamik Liu Palamara, JHEP 2019

Heavy Neutral Leptons

Ballett Pascoli Ross-Lonergan JHEP 2017
Kelly Machado PRD 2021

Higgs Scalar Portal

Pat Wilczek 2006
Batell Berger Ismail PRD 2019
MicroBooNE 2021

Axion-like Particles

Kelly Kumar Liu PRD 2021
Brdar et al PRL 2021

SBND Physics – PRISM (Precision Reaction Independent Spectrum Measurement)

- Proximity to the beam target and 74 cm offset, provides SBND with wide angular coverage in the range $[0^\circ, 1.6^\circ]$ relative to the BNB beam center
- Signals that vary as a function of neutrino energy or off-axis angle can be studied

Detector Overview: TPC

- Active mass: 112 ton
- Active volume: $4 \times 4 \times 5 \text{ m}^3$

Field Cage:
Surrounds the detector, to provide a uniform electric field of 500 V/cm

- Anode Plane assembly:**
- One on each end of the detector
 - $\sim 11,000$ wires in total
 - 3 mm wire spacing
 - Wire orientation at 0° and $\pm 60^\circ$ to the vertical

- Cathode Plane assembly:**
- Splits the detector into two drift volumes
 - At 100 kV

Detector Overview: PDS & CRT

TPB-coated reflective foils

PDS boxes

Photon Detection System

24 PDS boxes behind the anode planes, containing 120 PMTs and 192 X-ARAPUCAs

Coated PMT Uncoated X-ARAPUCA

Uncoated PMT Coated X-ARAPUCA

Cosmic Ray Taggers

- Seven walls surrounding the cryostat
- 146 modules containing scintillator strips with SiPM readout

Timeline

September 2022
**TPC & PDS
completed**

April 2023
**TPC lowered
into cryostat**

July 2024
**HV ramp to
100kV**

December 2024 – July 2025
Run 1

October 2025
Run 2 start

2022

2023

2024

2025

2026

December 2022
Detector move

March 2024
LAr filling

September 2024
CRT completed

TPC Performance: Noise

- Low TPC noise is a key performance metric for precise ionisation charge and calorimetry measurements
- In SBND, TPC electronics noise (dependent on wire length) is close to the intrinsic floor
- Very high signal-to-noise is achieved across all planes

TPC Calibrations

Electron Lifetime

Electron lifetime is consistently above 30ms, which is an order of magnitude greater the design value (3ms) and the maximum drift time (1.3ms).

Implies high argon purity.

Electric Field Uniformity

Distortions in the electric field can be caused by the accumulation of positively charged argon ions, referred to as the space charge effect.

This effect causes offsets of less than 1cm in SBND.

dE/dx

Muon and proton dE/dx both show good agreement with the expected most probable value (MPV) from theory.

This demonstrates accurate charge calorimetry.

PDS Performance

- SBND's high anode photocoverage and reflective, wavelength-shifting cathode provide excellent light detection efficiency
- Light detection efficiency is relatively uniform as a function of drift distance
- These features mean drift distance can be estimate using light information alone, by comparing signals from coated and uncoated PMTs

CRT Performance

- CRT modules detect charged particles with few-cm position and few-ns timing precision
- The primary role is to identify and reject cosmic-ray backgrounds
- CRTs have been essential in tagging cosmic-ray muons for calibration analyses
- CRT modules have been tuned for uniformity

 SBND Preliminary
CRT Off-Beam Data

CRT can resolve BNB bunch sub-structure!

Each bucket is around 3.5ns wide

SBND Operations

SBND Run 1 Cumulative POT

- Run 1 took place between December 2024 and July 2025 (3.5×10^{20} POT)
- Run 2 started in October 2025 and is ongoing!
- SBND already has the worlds largest ν -Ar dataset, having collected ~ 3 million neutrino interactions

Towards First Results!

ν_μ CC inclusive

ν_e CC inclusive

ν_μ CC $1\mu 1p 0\pi$

Summary and Outlook

- SBND has had a very successful first run, collecting the world's largest ν -Ar dataset
- Initial detector studies show great performance and that the detector is well-understood
- First preliminary cross-section analyses have been produced very early in experimental operations
- Many more analyses across our physics program are reaching mature stages

Look out for upcoming SBND physics results!

SBND collaboration Meeting at Fermilab, December 2025

Backup

TPC Signal Processing

Raw

Post-processing

